

Analysis of Growth, Trends, and Future of Organic Skincare Cosmetic Industry by Applying E-commerce Strategies

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A b s t r a c t

The main purpose of this study is to identify, examine, and analyse the recent and future trends and growth of the organic skincare industry by opting for e-commerce and other market strategies. This study identifies the current scenario of the organic skincare industry and the future growth of organic skincare products by comparing the recent growth and future possibilities of growth in both areas towards organic skincare cosmetics, and identifying the various strategies adopted by marketers for the growth of organic cosmetic products. This study is based on secondary data obtained by comparing the preferences and demands of cosmetic products via e-commerce. The data are collected through the official or main websites of the organic skincare growth and future perspective reviews by analysing the trends, etc., websites with their shares, demand, preferences, and future of the organic skincare industry. The objective of this study is to identify the current perspectives of marketers by applying marketing strategies to analyse the growth, trends, and future of organic skincare products by adapting e-commerce and other marketing strategies. The main motive of this study is to identify the marketing strategies of marketers for opting for changes in the strategies for changing the trends in the market and impacting other industries by opting for e-commerce strategies.

Keywords: Organic skincare, environmental concern, skincare cosmetics.

1. Introduction

Cosmetics are used widely and in many different ways to improve appearance. Cosmetics are used to alleviate acne, reduce the appearance of wrinkles, and reduce oil production. For a number of skin disorders, formulations such as skin protection, sunscreen, anti-acne, anti-wrinkle, and anti-aging are developed using a variety of components, either natural or artificial. India is the birthplace of producing organic, natural, Ayurveda, and many more herbs for the production of medicine, cosmetics, hair products, etc. A "cosmetic" is any product that aims to preserve, improve, or alter the appearance of the skin, hair & nails. Grooming and beauty products such as makeup, perfume, and skin cream are considered cosmetics. Maintenance of quality standards is essential when developing cosmetic formulations. The performance of a formulation should be on par with consumer expectations. Organic ingredients are used in cosmetic preparations for their wide range of properties, including anti-inflammatory, antiseptic, and antibacterial actions. Unfavourable side effects linked to skincare products created with synthetic chemicals are absent from these organic products. The popularity of these natural cures has led to an overstock of products in the Indian market, both socially and technologically (M.S. Ashawat, Madhuri Banchhor, Shailendra Saraf, and Swarnlata Saraf-2009). People tend to buy more eco-friendly, organic skincare products, together with an increase in income, rather than in line with educational achievement. The issue of consumers' lack of knowledge and the need to foster a culture where health and the environment come before other public concerns are once again brought to the forefront (Drăgan, Alina-Aida; Petrescu, Dacinia-Crina-2013). Retailers of organic skincare products might entice new clients by providing free samples. They might also collaborate with salon and cosmetic store proprietors to conduct co-marketing, a form of integrated management. Co-marketing strategies may cause consumers to become more aware of organic skincare's (Kumudhini, N. and Kumaran, S. S.-2020). Consumers opted to buy organic skincare items at the drugstore rather than online because they were more concerned about their health than about the environment. This research has significance for marketers, policymakers, and the government in increasing the consumption of organic skincare by bridging socioeconomic gaps and promoting sustainable development as a whole (Ainunnazlee Mohd Ali, Aini Mat Said, & Muhammad Zaem Mohd Salleh-2016).

Fig:1 Yearly growth rate of the manufacturing sector in India from fiscal years 2103 to 2022

Source: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/661391/manufacturing-industry-production-growth-rate-india/>

1.1 E-Commerce

“Electronic business is the general term for the buying and selling process that is supported by electronic means”-Philip Kotler. E-commerce, also referred to as e-commerce, has transformed the retail sector and grown to become a significant pillar of the global economy. This has been driven by the cosmetics industry, where mobile commerce has helped increase brands and profits. High-street fashion and cosmetic retailers have become big movers and innovators in building compelling and persuasive mobile e-commerce apps. However, the high-end and luxury industries have, until now, been reluctant to adapt and innovate at a comparable rate (Cristopher J. Parker & Stephn A. Doyle-2018).

Only around one in four consumers worldwide is said to prefer making electronics purchases offline to online in 2022. Most buyers who participated in the poll either showed a definite preference for online shopping or frequently used both channels when buying electronics.

Figure 2: Share of consumers who typically shop for electronics online versus offline worldwide by 2022.

Source- D. Tighe-2022.,<https://www.statista.com/statistics/1307801/online-or-offline-shopping-preference-for-electronics-world/>

1.2 Organic market

Consumers chose to purchase organic cosmetic products at the drugstore rather than online because they were more concerned about their health than the environment, according to Ainunnazlee Mohd Ali, Aini Mat Said, and Muhammad Zaem Mohd Salleh-2016. This study is important for marketers, decision-makers, and the government because it can help close socioeconomic gaps and advance sustainable development as a whole, which will enhance the use of organic cosmetics.

Customers' environmental concerns have increased over the past several years, and as a result, they prefer to buy goods from companies that employ environmentally friendly and sustainable production techniques (Ghazali et al., 2017). According to Soyoung Kim in Yoo-Kyoung Seock (2009), health and environmental concerns significantly influence the weight assigned to the attributes of beauty goods. Furthermore, consumers who scored highly on both health and environmental awareness were awarded significantly better ratings for natural beauty products than those who did not. Poor performers were significantly less willing to spend more money on natural beauty

products than other groups. Aisyah conducted a poll in 2017 and found that social media has a significant impact on the surge in demand for organic skincare products. This is because consumers, famous people, and influencers frequently publish personal endorsements of their preferred organic skincare and cosmetic products. This inspires their followers to practice social responsibility and purchase non-synthetic, naturally sourced, and ethically created goods. The growth of social media and e-commerce has contributed to the spread of this industry.

Table:1 Ingredients involved in producing organic skincare products

Classification of the ingredients:	Definition's
Synthetic	Chemically manufactured substances or materials are those that are created through chemical processes and do not naturally occur. (Beerling, 2014).
Natural	Any substance that has been extracted through harvesting, mining, or collection and subsequently processed without a chemical reaction (although physical procedures like washing, decolorizing, distilling, grinding/milling, separation, and/or concentration of the substance are permitted) to produce a chemical or chemicals that are discernible in the original source substance (Australian Society of Cosmetic Chemists, 2011; Beerling, 2014).
Natural derived	An ingredient is employed when a natural raw material serves as the foundation for a chemical reaction that creates one or more new chemicals that might not naturally occur or be present in the starting material (Beerling, 2014).
Organic	a naturally occurring substance that comes from organic farming practices, such as avoiding synthetic fertilizers, pesticides, plant growth regulators, and livestock feed additives; using crop rotation, integrated pest management, crop residues, animal manures, and mechanical cultivation to maintain soil productivity and tilth; and not using genetically modified organisms (GMOs). (Beerling, 2014).

Source: (S. Bom, J. Jorge, H.M. Ribeiro, J. Marto, 2019, Volume 225, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.03.255>).

1.3 Market overview

The following key points are derived from an analysis made by Aleksandra Łopaciuk & Mirosław Łoboda (2013) of the trends seen in the worldwide market for cosmetics at the beginning of the twenty-first century:

1. The demand for cosmetics will increase, mainly due to Asia's expanding markets. This will affect new spending and aid in the development of new product patterns and conceivably establish new aesthetic benchmarks.
2. International cosmetics manufacturers will need to set themselves apart to adapt their products to the changing market and the expectations of their new customers, which are influenced by non-Western cultures and acting in a unique manner.
3. The skincare sector has the biggest room for growth. It will continue to dominate the cosmetics market throughout the ensuing few years. The distribution network is evolving as supermarkets, hypermarkets,

and online retailers gain market share.

6. Cutting-edge science and technology are becoming increasingly the focus of new product debuts. However, there is a growing market for sustainably produced organic items that typically adhere to the fair-trade principle.

The size of the global organic skincare market was estimated at USD 9.82 million in 2021, and at a CAGR of 8.93%, it is predicted to grow to USD 21.21 billion by 2030.

1.4 Indian Report Overview for Organic Skincare Products

The market for anti-pollution skincare products was valued at \$9.07 billion globally in 2018 and is anticipated to grow at a CAGR of 4.2% from 2019 to 2025. The demand for the product will increase as consumer knowledge of the damaging effects of pollution levels on the skin increases, encouraging market expansion. Outdoor pollution has increased by 8% since 2016. Hence, during the projected period, the market will rise due to the rising demand for natural and organic cosmetics that are high in vitamins and antioxidants.

Figure-3

Source- www.grandviewresearch.com

1.5 Organic skincare market forecasts & analysis

The organic skin care product market is segmented by type, including body care, distribution channel, and region. Skincare is an important self-care component. The makeup procedure involves everything from prevention to correction. Advancements and innovations in the cosmetics sector promise to provide better goods with a focus on health. For quite some time, there has been a large supply of makeup with skincare advantages. The market for organic and natural skincare products is expanding due to factors such as skin sensitivity and awareness of the dangers of synthetic and chemical goods. The majority of consumers prefer to purchase goods labelled as natural or organic. Typically, they do not pay attention to the substances used to make the product. The facial care segment includes cleansers, moisturisers, oils/serums, and other facial care products. Geographically, the division comprises North America (which includes the United States, Canada, Mexico, and the rest of North America), Europe (which includes the United Kingdom, Germany, Spain, France, Italy, Russia, and the rest of Europe), Asia-Pacific (which includes China, Japan, India, Australia, and the rest of Asia-Pacific), South America (which

includes Brazil, Argentina, and the rest of South America), and the Middle East and Africa (United Arab Emirates, South Africa, and Rest of Middle East and Africa). The study provides the market size and values in (USD million) for the aforementioned forecast period.

Due to concerns regarding skin sensitivity, the presence of toxic substances in beauty and face creams can result in rashes and allergies. Daily use of excessive makeup can make the face wrinkly, harsh, and lose its natural hyaluronic acid. These are a few reasons why people choose organic products more often because they have fewer dangerous chemicals and more advantages than natural ingredients. Men's skincare products are becoming more popular as consumer knowledge increases, despite the market's abundance of items for women's skincare. Acne can be caused by environmental factors, such as pollution and UV radiation, that harm skin cells. Organic products reduce acne and shield the skin from UV radiation. These elements are anticipated to accelerate the market's growth for organic skincare products over the next five years. (Over the following five years, the market for organic skincare products is anticipated to grow at a CAGR of 8.72%).

Table 2: Industry segmentation for organic skincare products and export parabens of organic skincare products in India in 2021

Type	Facial Care	Cleansers Moisturizers and Oils/Serums Other Facial Care Products
	Moisturizers	Body Care Body Lotions Body Wash Other Body Care Products
Distribution Channel	Supermarkets/Hypermarkets Convenience Stores Specialist Stores Online Retail Stores Other Distribution Channel	
	North America	United States Canada Mexico Rest of North America
	Europe	United Kingdom Germany Spain France Italy Russia Rest of Europe
Geography	Asia-Pacific	China Japan India Australia Rest of Asia-Pacific

South America	Brazil Argentina Rest of South America
Middle East and Africa	United Arab Emirates South Africa Rest of Middle East and Africa

<https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/organic-skin-care-market>

Fig 3:

<https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/organic-skin-care-market>

he most commonly used preservatives in pharmaceutical and cosmetic products are parabens. Owing to its numerous adverse effects, consumers are increasingly worried about avoiding parabens as a component in their skincare products. They can irritate the skin and interfere with hormones. Synthetic chemicals such as propylparaben and butylparaben are no longer regarded as safe due to the rise of organic products. The phrase "free from parabens" will often appear on a product's label if it is paraben-free. The lack of parabens is also indicated by labels such as isobutyl paraben and isopropyl paraben. Nevertheless, in the beauty sector, items containing parabens and other unfavourable compounds account for a sizeable portion of sales in several categories. These categories are now being replaced by skincare products without parabens. Renee Cosmetics introduced premium face oils in January 2021.

<https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/organic-skin-care-market>

In terms of several popular categories, such as skin care, sun care, hair care, colour cosmetics, deodorants, and perfumes, which are the most widely used in this region, Asia-Pacific is one of the most diverse and active marketplaces in the global cosmetics business. As a result, this area continues to hold promise as a global market for organic skincare goods. During the projection period, the Asia-Pacific region is anticipated to experience the fastest growth. The demand for organic skincare in this area is driven by an aging population, rising millennial populations, a growing awareness of organic products, and an increase in the number of working women. With advertising and discounts, market actors entice consumers to purchase organic goods. Given the market's need, they are growing their portfolios.

2. Scope & challenges

A revived system of conventional medicine, encompassing organic, natural, Ayurveda, etc., comes from India, as was already said. Because of the rich flora in these systems, plants have been used for straightforward treatment since ancient times. Traditional medicine practitioners and local believers have tried to preserve the appearance, texture, and beauty of their patients' skin by employing native flora in cosmetics in various parts of India.

- Currently, 80% of the world's population still uses organic products because they are in harmony with nature and pose no health risks; several of them have traditional and scientific justifications that are based on animal experimentation and ethnobotanical research, and by consulting well-known, verified, and widely acknowledged books on natural systems of medicines and cosmetics, where the effects and safety are time-tested. Based on recent claims and conclusions reported in the literature review, the plants chosen for the current investigation were.
- It promotes a healthy life for the human skin.
- It is used to upgrade the texture of the skin to avoid chemical reactions.
- This supports the environmental concern.

3. Suggestions and Discussion

Analysing the growth trends and future of the organic skincare cosmetic industry and e-commerce requires the consideration of various factors, including consumer preferences, market dynamics, sustainability trends, and technological advancements. Here is an analysis of these aspects:

1. Consumer Shift Towards Organic and Natural Products

Consumers are becoming increasingly conscious of the ingredients in skincare products, leading to a growing demand for organic and natural alternatives. This trend is driven by concerns about the environment and personal health.

The organic skincare industry is expected to benefit from this shift as consumers seek products with fewer chemicals, preservatives, and artificial additives.

2. Sustainability and Eco-friendly Practices

Sustainability and eco-friendliness have become integral to the organic skincare industry. Companies are focusing on sustainable sourcing, eco-friendly packaging, and reducing their carbon footprint.

Brands that prioritise sustainable practices are likely to gain a competitive edge and attract environmentally conscious consumers.

3. E-Commerce Growth:

E-commerce plays a crucial role in the growth of the organic skincare industry. It provides consumers with convenient access to a wide range of products and allows smaller niche brands to reach a global audience. The COVID-19 pandemic further accelerated the shift towards online shopping, making e-commerce an essential distribution channel for skincare products.

4. Digital Marketing and Social Media Influence

Digital marketing and social media have become powerful tools for promoting organic skincare products. Brands leverage influencers, user-generated content, and educational content to engage and inform consumers.

Social media platforms such as Instagram and TikTok have become platforms for showcasing skincare routines and product recommendations.

5. Technological Advancements

Technology is driving innovation in the organic skincare industry with the development of clean beauty apps and tools for personalised skincare routines.

Advancements in product formulations, such as the use of AI and data analytics for personalised skincare regimens, are likely to reshape the industry.

6. Regulatory Environment:

The organic skincare industry is influenced by regulations and certifications such as USDA Organic and COSMOS Organic. Compliance with these standards is crucial for building trust among consumers.

7. Market Expansion and Diversification

The organic skincare industry is likely to expand beyond traditional skincare products to areas such as hair care, makeup, and personal hygiene.

Diversification into new product categories allows companies to capture a broader market share.

8. Challenges:

Despite its growth potential, the organic skincare industry faces challenges related to supply chain sustainability, ingredient sourcing, and premium price points for organic products.

Competition in e-commerce is intense and requires brands to invest in

marketing and customer engagement.

5. Future Outlook:

The organic skincare cosmetic industry is poised for sustained growth driven by consumer demand for clean and sustainable products. E-commerce remains a key driver, with brands leveraging digital marketing and technology to connect with consumers. Sustainable practices continue to be a crucial factor for success. The industry's future will likely see further innovation in product formulation, packaging, and a broader range of organic and natural products.

To thrive in this dynamic landscape, companies should prioritise transparency and sustainability and adapt to changing consumer preferences. Moreover, regulatory compliance and international market expansion will play pivotal roles in shaping the future of the organic skincare and e-commerce sectors.

6. Conclusion

As per the data retrieved from various websites and research papers, it can be concluded that regardless of price, people from a variety of socioeconomic groups frequently choose organic skincare products. Free samples, environmental concerns, and marketing are key factors that influence consumer decisions to buy organic skincare products. According to the evaluation and analysis, the market for organic skincare products will grow to \$9.07 billion in 2019 and to even higher levels by 2025. Predicted growth of organic cosmetics, moisturisers, anti-pollution products, and other skincare products. China shipped the most organic skincare products in 2021. Hence, the findings revealed that the majority of buyers usually preferred to shop for the products of their choice, mostly through e-commerce, as this is the easiest process for shopping and taking the details of anything very easily.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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References

- Ashawat M.S., Banchhor Madhuri, Saraf Shailendra, and Saraf Swarnlata, 2009, Herbal Cosmetics: "Trends in Skin Care Formulation", Vol, 3, Issue 5, pp- 82-89.
- Ghazali, E, Soon, PC, Mutum, DSandNguyen, B(2017). Health and cosmetics: Investigating consumers' values for buying organic personal care products. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*,39, 154-163.
- Aisyah, M (2017). Consumer demand for halal cosmetics and personal care products in Indonesia, *Al-Iqtishad Journal of Islamic Economics*,9(1), 125-142.
- Boonpreda Napasorn and Ruan Ximing,2020., AN INVESTIGATION OF THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON BUSINESS VALUE AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF ORGANIC SKIN CARE BRANDS IN THAILAND. Vol. 3(2): pp49 -64.

- Alina-Aida Drăgan; Petrescu, Crina Dacina, 2013, Consumer behaviour towards organic, natural and conventional skin care products: a pilot study, Vol. 5, ISSN. 3.
- N. Kumudhini, and S.S. Kumaran, 2020, Factors Influencing Purchase Intention towards Organic and Natural Cosmetics, ISSN 2465-6399.
- Ali, A.M., Said, A.M., Salleh, M.Z.M. (2016). Demographic Profile and Purchasing Pattern of Organic Skincare Products.
- Abdullah, M., Yahya, W., Ramli, N., Mohamed, S., Ahmad, B. (Eds). *Regional Conference on Science, Technology, and Social Sciences (RCSTSS 2014)*. Springer, Singapore.
- Organic Skin Care Market Size, Share & Trends Analysis Report by Product (Face Cream & Moisturizers, Face Cleanser, Face Serum, Body Wash), By Distribution Channel, By Region, And Segment Forecasts, 2022 – 2030., 978-1-68038-713, pp-70., Bom, S.; Jorge, J.; Ribeiro, H.M.; Marto, J. (2019). A Step Forward on Sustainability in the Cosmetics Industry: A Review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, (), S0959652619309655-. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.03.255
- Beerling, J., 2014. Green formulations and ingredients: Sahota, A. (Ed.) *Sustainability: How the cosmetics industry is greening up*. John Wiley and Sons, London.
- Beerling, J., Sahota, A. (2014). Green standards, certification, and indices in Sahota, A. (Ed.) *Sustainability: How the cosmetics industry is greening up*. John Wiley and Sons, London.
- Benabid F. Z., Zouai, F., 2016. Natural polymers: cellulose, chitin, chitosan, gelatin, starch, carrageenan, xylan, and dextran. *Alger. J. Nat. Prod.* 4, 348–357.
- Mohd Ali Ainunnazlee, Mat Said Aini, and Zaem Mohd Salleh Muhammad -2016., Demographic Profile and Purchasing Pattern of Organic Cosmetic Products, pp 899–907.
- Stephn A.Doyle &Christopher.J.Parker.,(2018)., Designing indulgent interaction: luxury fashion, m-commerce,ubermentch.,
- Łopaciuk Aleksandra & Łoboda Mirosław, -2013., GLOBAL BEAUTY INDUSTRY TRENDS IN THE 21st CENTURY.
- Kim Soyoun in Yoo-Kyoung,2009., Impacts of health and environmental consciousness on young female consumers' attitude towards and purchase of natural beauty products., Volume33, Issue 6, Pages 627-638.